

INVESTOR'S BEHAVIOUR BIASES ON INVESTMENT DECISIONS IN TAMILNADU

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Abstract

This study was corroborated an Investor's behaviour biases on investment decisions in Tamilnadu. The study is used to descriptive research design. From this, 100 investors are used for this study. The objective of the major study is to investor's behaviour bias on investment decision. It is found that Herding effect, Disposition effect, Regret aversion, Recency, Self-attribution bias, Hindsight bias, Conservatism bias, Loss aversion, Overconfidence and Anchoring are positively influence on investment decision. Home bias and Framing are negatively influence on investment decision.

Keywords: Overconfidence, Recency, Herding, Anchoring, investment decisions

INTRODUCTION

Behavioral finance is the study of psychology related to the financial decision-making processes taken by individuals and institutions. Sha and Ismail (2020) stated that investors make decisions depending upon the available information from the market, and the issue is related to how they build their of information. In this context, the investors should be aware of the different types of cognitive biases that may lead them to a much better or worst position. It was found that the investors are influenced by behaviour biases on investment decision.

Shefrin (2002) described that recognition of the existing risk from an investor sentiment or the risk that arises due to psychological factors that are sometimes larger than the fundamental risk. It was corroborated by John Jacob & Jayakrishnan (2015) stated that the various biases that occur can be detrimental, as it can lead to a risk miscalculation that may occur. Besides, such biases are also difficult to control because they are invisible and directly linked to thought processes involving emotions or feelings. Olsen (1998) warned that the main purpose of behavioral finance understands the influence of psychological factors systematically in the financial market so that each individual will be more prudent in decision making.

BEHAVIORAL BIASES

Overconfidence

Investors are highly optimistic confident about the trading outcomes and make sound investment decisions. Investors relate the high performance of the market to their own performance and ignore the fact that paying too much attention to their own capabilities and ignoring other factors can make them incur huge losses in the future.

Disposition effect

Disposition effect was proposed by Shefrin and Statman (1985). Investors' Disposition effect is affecting investment in the stock market. Investors tend to sell superior stocks and they are holding the losing stocks for a long time. An investor tends to avoid the loss than gain. The final decisions of the investors always perceived gains, not perceived loss.

Herding effect

It was introduced by Kahneman and Tversky (1979). Herding refers to follow the decisions of the other investors. Herding investors always make the decision depending up on other investors in the stock market. Investors rely on the collective information from private information. These results can price deviations from the fundamental values and the risk of reduced returns.

Mental accounting

It was initially coined by Thaler (1985). This theory implies that investors divide their investments in various portfolios on the basis of their own mental assumption. Investors are having separate mental account for investment policies. The purpose of the investor is to maximization of returns with the minimization of risk. This could result in the selection of those portfolios that are not profitable yet they satisfy the emotions of the investors

Confirmation bias

Confirmation bias coined by English psychologist Peter Wason, is the tendency of people to favour information that confirms or strengthens their beliefs, (Plous, Scott, 1993) People have a preconceived impression of rely on this information. This makes them adjust the future information to suit their opinion. These results were irrational decisions on their investment.

Hindsight bias

An investor predicted reasonably event and taking some decision. The investor has believes the happening of some event so that they can predicted. But it is dangerous as the investor can form cause and effect relationship between the two events. The investor believes is not correct for all time/ events. Hence, the result is irrational decisions. **Hindsight bias** proposed by Fischhoff and Beyth (1975)

House money effect

House money effect was given by Thaler and Johnson (1990). It refers to gamblers are earning more profits then they getting less loss-averse and willing to take the risk. So the investors who are making huge profits are willing to take more risk.

Endowment effect

It was originated by the paper of Kahneman et al. (1990). People pay too much emphasis on what they currently hold and do not want to change their position. This attitude makes the prices of profitable securities. Hence, the money stayed in the market so suffers from the ignorance of the people

Loss aversion

Loss aversion bias was given by Benartzi and Thaler (1995); people assumed at various aspect like assured losses and assured profits. Most of the investors make profit then they do not want to take any risk while investment. Whether there are any chances of losses, then they are ready to take more risks. They give more value towards uncertainty of loss than certainty losses

Framing

This bias was given by Tversky and Kahneman (1981). When the information is provided in the positive frame, investors avoid risk to make sure profit and when the same information is provided in the negative frame, they are ready to take the risk to avoid losses.

Home bias

This was introduced by French and Poterba (1991). The feeling of belongingness of the investors toward their domestic companies makes them invest in the domestic companies even if their returns are lower than those of the international companies. Thus, the investors become inclined toward home bias.

Self-attribution bias

People attribute their success to their own hard work and intelligence, while they blame their failure to the action of others or to some outside factors. It was originated by Bem (1967).

Conservatism bias

It was developed by Edwards (1982). It is refers to people stick to their own beliefs and forecasts but they are not willing to accept the information for their decision-making.

Regret aversion

When the people taking regret decision, that result may be greater impact on their future decisions. They either become motivated to take more risk or resist taking any risk at all. Investor should be avoid the regret aversion while any feeling of regret in the future. Regret aversion was found in the following three different papers, Bell (1982), Loomes and Sugden (1982).

Recency

The decisions of the investors are based on some recent events that are in news and they neglect the information that might be useful but have taken place quite a while ago. The investors taking a recent events and news based on making same decision is called Recency biases. They neglect the ago information/events that might be useful for decision.

Anchoring

Anchoring bias was introduced by Tversky and Kahneman (1981). The investors make their investment decision based on their past information they are gathering from their previous investment. The successive decisions are anchored around some previous information.

Representativeness

A representativeness bias was introduced by Kahneman and Tversky. Representativeness means assessing the characteristics of an event or object. This makes them to consider the event/object more likely to happen which may or may not happen.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- The Major focal point of this study is to find out the selected behaviour bias factors on equity investors' investment decision.
- To test the relationship between investor's bias and Investment decision
- To analyze the factors influence an investor's bias on Investment decision

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

- Ho: There is no relationship between investor's bias and Investment decision
- Ho: investor's bias does not influence the Investment decision

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is used to descriptive research design. The study is focused on factors influence an investor's bias on Investment decision. The present study considers the Investment decision is a dependent variable. Here, Overconfidence, disposition effect, herding effect, mental accounting, confirmation bias, hindsight bias, house money effect, endowment effect, home bias, loss aversion, framing, self-attribution bias, conservatism bias, regret aversion, Recency, anchoring and representativeness considered as an independent variables. Based on this, 100 investors are drawn by purposive sampling technique. From this, 100 investors companies are used for this study. After collecting the data it was entered in to SPSS package for the further analysis. In order to answer the research objectives and test the hypothesis, relevant statistical tools are applied.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 1 explains an investor's opinion towards investment biases during investment. Mean and standards deviation are calculated from the collected data. herding effect (4.34), mental accounting (4.12), disposition effect (4.05), self-attribution bias (4.08), regret aversion (4.00), endowment effect (3.96), home bias (3.94), loss aversion (3.94), framing (3.88), Overconfidence (3.85), conservatism bias (3.84), house money effect (3.79), hindsight bias (3.77), confirmation bias (3.68), representativeness (3.64), Recency (3.43), and anchoring (3.45). It is found that herding effect, mental accounting, disposition effect, self-attribution bias, regret aversion, endowment effect, home bias, loss aversion, framing, Overconfidence and conservatism bias are high opinion towards investment behaviour bias of the investors. House money effect, hindsight bias, confirmation bias, representativeness, Recency, and anchoring are moderate opinion towards investment behaviour bias of the investors.

Table 1: An Investor's Opinion towards Investment Biases

Dimensions	Mean	standard deviation
Overconfidence	3.85	1.112
Disposition effect	4.05	1.085
Herding effect	4.34	1.161
Mental accounting	4.12	.968
Confirmation bias	3.68	1.453
Hindsight bias	3.77	1.223
House money effect	3.79	1.236
Endowment effect	3.96	1.360
Loss aversion	3.94	1.354
Framing	3.88	1.303
Home bias	3.94	1.381
Self-attribution bias	4.08	1.374
Conservatism bias	3.84	1.221
Regret aversion.	4.00	1.315
Recency	3.43	1.439
Anchoring	3.45	1.447
Representativeness	3.64	1.432

Source: Primary data computed

Table 2 explains an investor's opinion towards investment decision. Mean and standards deviation are calculated from the collected data. The mean values are they make investment decisions before to know the market fundamentals of underlying stocks. (3.10), they consider carefully the price changes of stocks (4.72), they avoid selling shares that have decreased in value and readily sell shares that have increased in value (3.23), they hold losing stocks too long than about selling winning stocks too soon (4.17), they use trend analysis of some representative stocks (4.16), they usually react quickly to the changes of other investors' decisions and follow their reactions to the stock market (3.73), they were more risk seeking than usual (3.86), they skills and knowledge of stock market can help them to outperform the market (4.16), Market information is important for your stock investment (4.44), element of their investment portfolio separately (4.22), they become more risk adverse after got a prior loss (4.85), they forecast the changes in stock prices in the future based on the recent stock prices (4.76), they ignore the connection between different investment possibilities (4.22), they put the past trends of stocks (4.86), their previous experiences in the market for their next investment (4.56), they buy 'hot' stocks and avoid stocks that have performed poorly in the recent past (4.76), Other investors' decisions of choosing stock types have impact on their investment decisions (4.79), Other investors' decisions of buying and selling stocks have impact on your investment decisions (4.79), close friends and relatives as the reliable reference for their investment decisions (4.21). It is found that price changes of stocks, hold losing stocks too long than about selling winning stocks too soon, element of investment portfolio,

investment possibilities, performed in the recent stock prices, and close friends and relatives as the reliable reference are higher opinion towards investment decision while investing the securities.

Table 2: An Investor's Opinion towards Investment Decision

Investment decision statement	Mean	Standard deviation
I make investment decisions before to know the market fundamentals of underlying stocks.	3.10	1.00
I consider carefully the price changes of stocks	4.72	0.45
I avoid selling shares that have decreased in value and readily sell shares that have increased in value.	3.23	1.16
I hold losing stocks too long than about selling winning stocks too soon.	4.17	0.38
I use trend analysis of some representative stocks	4.16	0.37
I usually react quickly to the changes of other investors' decisions and follow their reactions to the stock market.	3.73	0.44
After a prior gain, you are more risk seeking than usual.	3.86	0.81
I believe that your skills and knowledge of stock market can help you to outperform the market.	4.16	0.37
Market information is important for your stock investment.	4.44	0.72
I tend to treat each element of your investment portfolio separately.	4.22	0.41
After a prior loss, you become more risk averse.	4.85	0.36
I forecast the changes in stock prices in the future based on the recent stock prices.	4.76	0.43
I ignore the connection between different investment possibilities.	4.22	0.41
I put the past trends of stocks	4.86	0.35
I rely on my previous experiences in the market for my next investment.	4.56	0.79
I buy 'hot' stocks and avoid stocks that have performed poorly in the recent past.	4.76	0.43
Other investors' decisions of choosing stock types have impact on your investment decisions.	4.79	0.41
Other investors' decisions of buying and selling stocks have impact on your investment decisions.	4.79	0.41
I consider my close friends and relatives as the reliable reference for your investment decisions.	4.21	0.41

Source: Primary data computed

Table 3: Relationship between investor's bias and Investment decision

Dimensions	R-value	P-value
Overconfidence	0.630	0.001*
Disposition effect	0.540	0.001*
Herding effect	0.607	0.001*
Mental accounting	0.534	0.001*
Confirmation bias	0.685	0.001*
Hindsight bias	0.642	0.001*
House money effect	0.686	0.001*
Endowment effect	0.634	0.001*
Loss aversion	0.624	0.001*
Framing	0.587	0.001*
Home bias	0.624	0.001*
Self-attribution bias	0.677	0.001*
Conservatism bias	0.514	0.001*
Regret aversion.	0.377	0.001*
Recency	0.491	0.001*
Anchoring	0.525	0.001*
Representativeness	0.601	0.001*

Source: Primary data computed; * significant at one present level

Ho: There is no relationship between investor's bias and Investment decision

Pearson Correlation analysis has been applied to find out the relationship between investor's bias and Investment decision in the result is displayed table 3.

Here, Overconfidence, disposition effect, herding effect, mental accounting, confirmation bias, hindsight bias, house money effect, endowment effect, home bias, loss aversion, framing, self-attribution bias, conservatism bias, regret aversion, Recency, anchoring and representativeness considered as an independent variables and Investment decision is treated as a dependent variable. The correlation values are House money effect (0.686), Confirmation bias (0.685), Self-attribution bias (0.677), Hindsight bias (0.642), Endowment effect (0.634), Overconfidence (0.630), Herding effect (0.607), Home bias (0.624), Loss aversion (0.624), Representativeness (0.601), Framing (0.587), Mental accounting (0.534), Disposition effect (0.540), Anchoring (0.525), Conservatism bias (0.514), Recency (0.491), and Regret aversion (0.377).

It is found that House money effect, Confirmation bias, Self-attribution bias, Hindsight bias, Endowment effect, Overconfidence, Herding effect, Home bias, Loss aversion, and Representativeness are highly related to investment decision. Framing, mental accounting, Disposition effect, Anchoring and Conservatism bias are low level related to investment decision.

Table 4: factors influencing investor’s bias and Investment decision

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	F	Sig.
0.906	0.820	0.819	0.36793	585.479	0.001*

Predictors	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	-0.438	0.089	-	8.694	0.000
Overconfidence	0.52	0.028	0.483	18.377	0.000
Disposition effect	0.526	0.023	0.528	22.787	0.000
Herding effect	0.779	0.034	0.712	23.017	0.000
Mental accounting	0.065	0.045	0.092	1.451	0.147
Confirmation bias	-0.057	0.033	-0.095	-1.751	0.081
Hindsight bias	0.118	0.037	0.197	3.168	0.002
House money effect	-0.008	0.035	-0.013	-0.222	0.825
Endowment effect	0.013	0.034	0.021	0.383	0.702
Loss aversion	0.113	0.035	0.176	3.223	0.001
Framing	-0.105	0.034	-0.159	-3.115	0.002
Home bias	-0.075	0.034	-0.122	-2.195	0.029
Self-attribution bias	0.122	0.03	0.186	4.109	0.000
Conservatism bias	0.114	0.032	0.185	3.619	0.000
Regret aversion.	0.435	0.045	0.727	9.596	0.000
Recency	0.177	0.033	0.258	5.284	0.000
Anchoring	0.074	0.033	0.111	2.257	0.024
Representativeness	-0.019	0.03	-0.027	-0.644	0.520

Source: Primary data computed; * significant at one present level; ** significant at five present level; (NS) Non-significant

Table 4 explains the factors influencing investor’s bias and Investment decision. The Regression analysis is applied to know the effect of exploratory variables on the dependent variable. Here, Overconfidence, disposition effect, herding effect, mental accounting, confirmation bias, hindsight bias, house money effect, endowment effect, home bias, loss aversion, framing, self-attribution bias, conservatism bias, regret aversion, Recency, anchoring and representativeness considered as an independent variables and Investment decision is treated as a dependent variable. The adjusted r-square value is found to be 0.819. It is found that the exploratory variables such as Overconfidence, disposition effect, herding effect, mental accounting, confirmation bias, hindsight bias, house money effect, endowment effect, home bias, loss aversion, framing, self-attribution bias, conservatism bias, regret aversion, Recency, anchoring and representativeness are influenced the Investment decision at 81.9 percent.

Ho: investor's bias does not influence on Investment decision

The unstandardized co-efficient beta values indicate the strength of relationship between dependent and exploratory variables. It is expressed by the equation as follows;

Investment decision = -0.438 + 0.779 (Herding effect) + 0.526 (Disposition effect) + 0.52 (Overconfidence) + 0.435 (Regret aversion) + 0.177 (Recency) + 0.122 (Self-attribution bias) + 0.118 (Hindsight bias) + 0.114 (Conservatism bias) + 0.113 (Loss aversion) + 0.074 (Anchoring) -0.075 (Home bias)-0.105 (Framing)

It is inferred that exploratory variable have increased to investment decision, herding factors has creased at 0.0779 percent, and disposition has increased at 0.526 level, overconfidence has increased at 0.52 regret aversion has increased at 0.435 level, Recency has increased at 0.177, self-attribution bias has increased at 0.122 level, hindsight bias has increased at 0.118 level, conservatism bias has increased at 0.144 level, loss aversion has increased at 0.113 level, Home bias has decreased at 0.075, Framing has negative impact on 0.105 level. It is found that Herding effect, Disposition effect, Regret aversion, Recency, Self-attribution bias, Hindsight bias, Conservatism bias, Loss aversion, Overconfidence and Anchoring are positively influence on investment decision. Home bias and Framing are negatively influence on investment decision.

Finding of the study

- It is found that herding effect, mental accounting, disposition effect, self-attribution bias, regret aversion, endowment effect, home bias, loss aversion, framing, Overconfidence and conservatism bias are high opinion towards investment behaviour bias of the investors. House money effect, hindsight bias, confirmation bias, representativeness, Recency, and anchoring are moderate opinion towards investment behaviour bias of the investors.
- It is found that price changes of stocks, hold losing stocks too long than about selling winning stocks too soon, element of investment portfolio, investment possibilities, performed in the recent stock prices, and close friends and relatives as the reliable reference are higher opinion towards investment decision while investing the securities.
- It is found that House money effect, Confirmation bias, Self-attribution bias, Hindsight bias, Endowment effect, Overconfidence, Herding effect, Home bias, Loss aversion, and Representativeness are highly related to investment decision. Framing, mental accounting, Disposition effect, Anchoring and Conservatism bias are low level related to investment decision.
- It is found that Herding effect, Disposition effect, Regret aversion, Recency, Self-attribution bias, Hindsight bias, Conservatism bias, Loss aversion, Overconfidence and Anchoring are positively influence on investment decision. Home bias and Framing are negatively influence on investment decision.

CONCLUSION

The finance theories are assumed that financial decisions have leads to gain profitable in investments. It can increase the wealth of the shareholders and investor's safeguards of their investment and potential to invest more and more. The theory of behavioral finance gave a vivid explanation about actual investor behavior and the factors influence of an investor behavior in different circumstances. The investors can take the advantage from the profitable share or securities when others don't have information about these opportunities. It is suggests that the make a properly planning can make money into great opportunities. The existence of the biases in the financial markets gives a momentum to the market. Investors can make their decisions on self-created principles. The quick decision-making can helps to grate impacts on the future investment decision.

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